

Evaluation of Child Friendly School in Building Student Character: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The character crisis is an issue of many countries. For many children, the school is an uncaring environment, that can cause a negative impact in mental health, so we can see the output of school residents is not in a good character. In fact, schools have an important role in the psychosocial development of children. Seeing this fact, UNICEF developed a child-friendly school program to solve the problem. Its also necessary to evaluate the child friendly school programme, then it will be discussed about CIPP model too. The results of the review found that child-friendly schools can be optimal if principals, teachers and education staff, and school committees collaborate well in carrying out their roles in realizing the six principal components of child-friendly schools. Research on this topic is limited and this article is a literature review, so it is necessary to conduct further research using interview and questionnaire methods related to the role of child-friendly schools in building student character.

KEYWORDS: Child Friendly School, Student Character, CIPP

1. INTRODUCTION

By look the situation of millennial generation nowadays, we found that many students who have not polite (such as talking with other when the teacher teaches, roam during the class) not discipline, not responsible in the school (don't want to do the task), and not enthusiast during the class. That behavior certainly reflects a character that not yet built properly. In fact, schools are not only a place for producing cognitively intelligent generations to the exclusion of character, but schools must be able to balance the cognitive, spiritual, physical-motor, language, and socio-emotional aspects of their students. Related to this, there is currently a child-friendly school program. Learning in a pleasant atmosphere is one of the top priorities in schools, especially for primary education as Barrow and Woods ^[1] found out that "the object of schooling is not to" transmit a body of knowledge "but to encourage students to" love learning for its own sake. The CFS model approach is a comprehensive concept that has so far been implemented in various countries. UNICEF ^[2] reported that about 56 countries had applied this model until 2007 with various interpretations, which is likely due to each country's local wisdoms or local educational contexts. The framework of CFS is motivated by a philosophy of children's rights, which considers the role of school to facilitate the development of the whole child ^[3].

Educators and education personnel in schools are expected to provide humane education and learning, so can facilitate the students to have educated character and behavior. Educated behavior is displayed in the form of academic achievement, showing ethical behavior and noble character, have high learning motivation, being creative, disciplined, responsible, and showing selfcharacter as a community, citizen, and nation.^[4] For this reason, schools as organizers of the education and learning process must apply learning systematically and continuously without physical-stress or psychological pressure to the students and not treat beyond the limits of the students abilities.

One of the goals of Child Friendly Schools is to built students with good character. The character has three parts, namely moral knowledge, moral feelings, and moral behavior. In the class and programs character education, all of parts is integrated each other.^[5] The good characters are consists by knowing the good, desiring the good, and doing the good habits. This good character is more clearly illustrated by the attitude of students who are polite, respect teachers in class, have high learning motivation, disciplined, and responsible to the school task.

To ensure the implementation of child-friendly school in educational units, it must have the principles of child protection; without violence, without discrimination, the best interests for the students, the right to grow and develop, respect with children's opinions, which can be integrated into other fields such as policies, curriculum, management, school regulations, facilities,

infrastructure, and the environment, as well as day-to-day relations between stakeholders.^[6] The principle of child protection when applied will make students feel that they have been given the best from the school. So, they feel a must to show the best of themselves by showing a good character.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Child Friendly School

One of the aims of implementing Child Friendly Schools is to form students with good character. The character has three interrelated parts, namely moral knowledge, moral feelings, and moral behavior. In practice, classes and programs character education, all of three approaches is often integrated. Characters are either consists of knowing the good, desiring the good, and did habits well. This good character is more clearly illustrated by the attitude of students who are polite, respect teachers in class, have high learning motivation, disciplined, and responsible by the school assignments was given. Child-friendly school might also be considered provisionally effective if the difference in achievement between the disadvantaged and the advantaged students was narrowing over time.^[7]

In a 2005 external evaluation confirmed that the terminology of the child-friendly school as an accessible, healthy, safe and attractive environment for children was becoming observably better recognized and accepted by all levels of stakeholders. The underlying CFS concept of the school as rights-based, inclusive, childseeking and effective for children's learning was becoming better understood by a core of senior policy-makers and technical officers at central and some provincial levels; and the scope of change implied by CFS with respect to policy, attitudes, behavior and systems coordination was gradually being more clearly articulated in operational terms.^[8]

Child-friendly schools must be effective with children. They must promote good quality teaching and learning, provide good quality materials and resources, enhance teachers capacity, moral, commitment, status, income and promote quality learning outcomes.^[9] And what is also important that the process of promoting child-friendly schools through curriculum development and teacher education is a complex one, as it requires of the teacher to understand the principles that underpin the thinking behind the change. It becomes an even bigger challenge for curriculum developers and teachers to ensure that there is practical implementation of what has been conceptualised beyond the theoretical level, and that this implementation is sustainable.^[10] Educational leadership for CFS must monitor the processes. It should be a continuous process not a one shot operation if at all implementation is to succeed. Strengths and weaknesses must be identified and make proposals for action basing on what is considered to be of "quality". The fundamental rationale and most critical reason for monitoring and evaluation is to enable implementing organizations (schools) to gauge progress and determine whether the model is working as expected. Innovations are often judged as failures when in fact they simply have not been properly implemented or given a chance to work. Every country needs to embrace this concept of quality which goes well beyond pedagogic excellence and purely academic performance outcomes. The focus should be on the needs of the child as a whole not just academic performance dimension that educators have concentrated on. People must dwell on a multi-dimensional coverage of quality and a holistic concern for the child's needs.

The school has met the requirement of the six essential components of child-friendly school, namely pedagogy, health, inclusiveness, gender sensitivity, community participation, and protection initiated by UNICEF in different additional terms and context. The facility has a significant impact on the realization of an ideal CFS for students. In applying the CFS program, the government must also incorporate elements of local culture in determining and developing the CFS program standard so that inconvenience arises from both teachers and students and the unpreparedness of students.^[11]

2.2. CIPP Model

There are many models of evaluation that can be used to evaluate a program. However, the most commonly used is the CIPP evaluation models. The CIPP evaluation model scale had four factors consisting of context, input, process and product. CIPP evaluation model developed by Stufflebeam and Shinkfield in 1985. The evaluation context is used to give a rational reason a selected program or curriculum to be implemented. A wide scale, context can be evaluated on: the program's objectives, policies that support the vision and mission of the institution, the relevant environment, identification of needs, opportunities and problems specific diagnosis. Evaluation input to provide information about the resources that can be used to achieve program objectives. Evaluation inputs used to: find a problem solving strategy, planning, and design programs. Evaluation process serves to provide feedback to individuals to account for the activities of the program or

curriculum. The evaluation process is conducted by: monitoring sources can potentially cause failure, prepare a preliminary information for planning decisions, and explain the process that actually happened. Product evaluation measure and interpret the achievement of goals. Evaluation of the products also come to: the measurement of the impact of the expected and unexpected. The evaluation is conducted: during and after the program. Stufflebeam and Shinkfield suggest product evaluation conducted for the four aspects of evaluation: impact, effectiveness, sustainability, and transportability. The decision making process is done by comparing the findings/facts contained in context, input, process and product standards or criteria that have been set previously.^[12]

The aim of the CIPP model attaching importance to process evaluation is to look into all the strategies and components of evaluation and to seek the answers to these questions: “Is evaluation design functioning properly?” “Which points are possibly the problematic ones and how can they be solved?” “Are there more efficient ways to collect the data?” Stufflebeam suggests evaluators to follow these steps, as a logical structure, to be used in designing each evaluation type: focusing the evaluation, collection of information, organization of information, analysis of information, reporting of information and administration of evaluation. One of the strengths of CIPP model is, especially, that it is a useful and simple tool for helping evaluators produce questions of vital importance to be asked in an evaluation process. Evaluators can determine lots of questions for each component of the CIPP model.^[13]

Figure 1. CIPP Model

2.3. Evaluation of Child Friendly School

When implemented effectively Child Friendly Schools realize UNICEF’s objectives. Based on the six country site visits, secondary sources that put the country visits in a global context, and other work AIR has carried out in Child Friendly Schools, the evaluation found the following:^[14]

- a. School heads, teachers, and parents in Child Friendly Schools view inclusiveness as a key principle of the CFS model and make efforts to include, encourage, and support students, regardless of gender or background. Schools make concerted efforts to retain children in school, and reach out to children not in school - although there was variation across countries in how much effort schools make. Child Friendly Schools provide inclusive classroom environments in which teachers demonstrate similar expectations for, and equal treatment of, all students regardless of background. The Child Friendly Schools visited appear to be particularly successful in creating an environment where female students feel safe, supported, and challenged.
- b. The majority of schools provide safe and comfortable environments conducive to learning (e.g., structurally sound buildings and classrooms, students protected from dangers such as toxic materials, sufficiently ventilated classrooms). During school visits we observed many beautiful schools, classrooms, and grounds—colorful murals, children’s artwork, well-cared for gardens, bright open spaces—that reflected the pride that students, teachers, staff, parents and the communities feel in their school and the extent to which they view such environments as important to being child friendly.

Most students feel that adults in their school provide important emotional supports and nearly all schools provide health education to support children's health and safety.

- c. Most schools in the six countries are successful in creating an environment that conveys to students that learning is important and worthwhile, encourages students' active engagement, and promotes learning. Teachers in most of the six countries are using child centered instructional techniques, are creating environments that encourage active learning as well as trust and respect, and convey an understanding of the principles of the CFS model regarding pedagogy. HLM analyses suggest that these child centered pedagogies contribute to positive conditions for learning where students feel safe, respected and included, challenged, and supported.
- d. There are high levels of student involvement in many schools; schools make substantial efforts to create a welcoming atmosphere for parents and encourage parent and community participation in school events and decision-making. HLM analyses suggest that family and community involvement (as reported by teachers) contributed to positive conditions for learning where students feel safe, respected and included, challenged, and supported.
- e. HLM analyses suggest that CFS Schools have created an environment where female students feel included. For example, female students consistently rated the three dimensions of school climate higher than male students.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This literature focuses in child-friendly school and evaluation by the CIPP model.

The review process began with a search engine, Google Scholar, to search for articles with keyword "child-friendly school in building student character", and also "CIPP model". The search ranged from 2004-2022. The criteria for inclusion in this study are:

- a. Qualitative results from child-friendly school
- b. Study case in one country
- c. Research carried out in the world

The steps to compiling this literature review "Evaluation of child friendly school in building student character" are as follows:

Step 1: Formulated the Problem

- Chose a topic that matches your problems and interests
- Problems must be written entirely and accurately

Step 2: Searched the Literature

- Searched for literature relevant to the research
- Got an overview of the research topic
- Research resources were beneficial if they are supported by knowledge related to the studied topic
- Sources must provide an overview/summary related to previous research.
- Paid attention to the contributions made by articles on the topic
- Paid attention to the data sources needed according to the needs of the topic.

Step 4: Analysis and Interpretation

Step 5: Discussed and summarized the literature

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section reports the main findings reviewed from several articles the author has read. The analysis selected most of the articles based on the child-friendly school resource. The articles that have been reviewed are research conducted in several countries in the world. The table describes the results of the literature review conducted by the author. Research has been carried out in several schools.

Table: Child-friendly school

No.	Author and Year	Title	Country	Method	Results
1	Chabbott, Colette (2004) ^[7]	UNICEF’s child-friendly schools: A desk review	Washington, DC	Desk review	CFS might also be considered provisionally effective if the Difference in achievement Between the disadvantaged And the advantaged students Was narrowing over time. This Last approach, however, calls
2	Bernard, Anne (2008) ^[8]	Evaluation of the processes, impact and future strategies of the child-friendly school programme	Cambodia	Study case	CFS framework recognizes that the best and most useful assessments need to be responsive, interactive and iterative, and that they need to be done through progressive, on-site analysis by those directly involved: directors, teachers, district offices, students themselves. While clearly sound in principle, however, this approach to CFS assessment is also proving a challenge to apply.
3.	Mandiudza, Leona (2013) ^[9]	Child friendly schools	Zimbabwe	Qualitative	Child-friendly schools must be effective with children. They must promote good quality teaching and learning, provide good quality materials and resources, enhance teachers capacity, moral, commitment, status, income and promote quality learning outcomes.
4.	Mpho Modipane & Mahlapahlapana Themane (2014) ^[10]	Teachers social capital as a resource for curriculum development: lessons learnt in the implementation of a child-friendly schools programme	South Africa	Qualitative	Teachers participation in the implementation of the child- friendly school improved their commitment to curriculum development.
5	Fitriani, Somariah, et al. (2021) ^[11]	A child-friendly school: how the school implements the model	Indonesia	Qualitative	The facility has a significant impact on the realization of an ideal CFS for students. In applying the CFS model, the government must also incorporate elements of local culture in determining and developing the CFS model standard so that inconvenience arises from both teachers and students and the unpreparedness of students.
6	Osher, David, et. al. (2009) ^[14]	UNICEF child friendly schools programming: Global evaluation final report	Washington, DC	Qualitative	Most schools in the six countries are successful in creating an environment that conveys to students that learning is important and worthwhile, encourages students active engagement, and promotes learning. Eighty-three to ninety-six percent of students reported satisfactory or excellent on the “Challenging Student-Centered Learning Environment”

5. CONCLUSION

This article aims to see how child-friendly school in building character student based on the literature review objectives from previous research. Most of the results of the literature review show that it is difficult to obtain literature related to CFS. One of the goals of Child Friendly Schools is to build students with good character. To ensure the implementation of child-friendly school in educational units, it must have the principles of child protection; without violence, without discrimination, the best interests for the students, the right to grow and develop, respect with children's opinions, which can be integrated into other fields such as policies, curriculum, management, school regulations, facilities, infrastructure, and the environment, as well as day-to-day relations between stakeholders. The authors are aware that the present study is not without limitations. Because of the chosen research procedure, this study may not have enabled complete coverage of all the articles in the field of child-friendly school in building student character. Yet, it seems reasonable to assume that the review process covered a large share of published studies available. Finally, this article proposes several directions for future research related to the importance of character, so it is necessary to continue to pay attention and evaluate child-friendly school programs.

REFERENCES

1. R. Barrow and R. Woods. 2006. An Introduction to philosophy of education, 4th Edition. London and New York: Routledge.
2. UNICEF. 2009. The child friendly school manual. New York: UNICEF Division of Communication.
3. E. Godfrey, *et al.* 2012. Cross-national measurement of school learning environments: creating indicators for evaluating UNICEF's child friendly schools initiative," *Child. Youth Serv. Rev.*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 546–557.
4. Rusmana, Ajang. 2017. Model Pengembangan Sekolah Ramah Anak Melalui Penguatan Budaya Sekolah di Sekolah Menengah Pertama (SMP). Repository UPI. http://repository.upi.edu/31059/4/D_PU_1103334_Chapter1.pdf. In access 17 October 2021.
5. Howard, R. W., Berkowitz, M. W., & Schaeffer, E. F. 2004. Politics of Character Education. SAGE Journal Educational Policy. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904803260031>. In access 17 October 2021.
6. Sholeh, M. A. N., Humaidi, L. 2016. Panduan Sekolah & Madrasah Ramah Anak. Penerbit Erlangga. Jakarta.
7. Chabbott, Colette. 2004. UNICEF's child-friendly schools: A desk review. ResearchGate. Washington DC.
8. Bernard, Anne. 2008. Evaluation of the processes, impact and future strategies of the child-friendly school programme. UNICEF. Cambodia.
9. Mandiudza, Leona. 2013. Child friendly schools. Zimbabwe. Greener Journal of Educational Research ISSN: 2276-7789 Vol. 3 (6), pp. 283-288, August 2013.
10. Mpho Modipane and Mahlapahlapana Themane. 2014. Teachers' social capital as a resource for curriculum development: lessons learnt in the implementation of a child-friendly schools programme. South Africa. South African Journal of Education, Volume 34, Number 4, November 2014
11. Fitriani, Somariah, *et. al.* 2021. A child-friendly school: how the school implements the model. International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE) Vol. 10, No. 1, March 2021, pp. 273~284.
12. Warju. 2016. Education program evaluation using CIPP model. Innovation of Vocational Technology Education. Vol 12 No. 1, January 2016. <https://ejournal.upi.edu/index.php/invotec/article/view/4502/3133>. In access 17 August 2022.
13. Hakan, Karatas, Fer Seval. 2011. CIPP evaluation model scale: development, reliability and validity. Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences Volume 15, Pages 592-599. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.03.146>. In access 17 August 2022.
14. Osher, David, *et. al.* 2009. UNICEF child friendly schools programming: Global evaluation final report. Washington, DC: American Institutes for Research.

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